

Removal of some toxic metal ions from water in a batch process using laterite

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Abstract : The potential use of laterite for the removal of some toxic metal ions viz. Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Fe^{II} from aqueous solution was investigated. The equilibrium was found to attain within two hours. At equilibrium the adsorption capacity was determined to be 73.6, 85.7, 44.6 and 90.5 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ respectively for Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Fe^{II} with particle size of 300 μm , dose of 1.0 g, agitation speed of 400 rpm and 303 K. The applicability of the process was determined by equilibrium, kinetic, thermodynamic and isotherm parameters. The interference and tolerance limit of different foreign ions on metal ions removal was evaluated. The removal efficiency >70% was obtained in spiked as well as bulk samples. The process was found to be efficient, easy and cost effective. Laterite as an adsorbent can be recommended as an alternative to active carbon for metal ions removal.

Keywords : Laterite, metal ions, adsorption, batch process.

Metal ions in water are of great concern now-a-days, because they originate from a wide variety of sources, both natural as well as anthropogenic and also due to their extreme toxicity¹.

Various physicochemical methods for removal of toxic metal ions from water include chemical precipitation, solvent extraction, ion exchange and membrane and adsorption process². Naturally occurring adsorbent like clay and minerals⁴ are preferred over the other adsorbents due to their easy availability and cost effectiveness. The present study reports the feasibility of naturally occurring clay, laterite, as the adsorbent, for the removal of some toxic metal ions viz. Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} and Fe^{II} from water.

Results and discussion

Air dried laterite sample was analysed following standard procedure⁵. The chemical composition of laterite being, SiO_2 : 67.2%, Al_2O_3 : 9.35%, Fe_2O_3 : 10.0%, Na_2O : 0.20%, K_2O : 2.73%, CaO : 0.03%, MgO : 1.0%, MnO_2 : 0.052%, TiO_2 : 1.27% and loss on ignition : 1.27%. The surface characterisation made following scanning electron microscopy and X-ray diffraction pattern indicates porous texture (containing cenosphere and pleosphere) and different mineral surface sites (viz. quartz, goethite, hematite and illite).

The effect of some major parameters, viz. contact time, agitation speed, dose and particle size of laterite, pH, temperature and metal ion concentration in solution on the uptake of metal ions have been investigated. The influence of foreign ions including the co-metal ions on the extent and efficiency of adsorption was also evaluated.

The adsorption of Cu^{II} ion at three different initial concentrations is plotted against agitation time (Fig. 1). Adsorption increases sharply at the initial stage and gradually reaches for an equilibrium. The extent of adsorption at equilibrium depends on its initial concentration: Equilibrium times are 45, 80, 90 and 120 min for Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Fe^{II} respectively. The extent of uptake for cop-

Fig. 1. Effect of contact time on the adsorption of Cu^{II} : (♦) 20 ppm, (○) 50 ppm, (Δ) 100 ppm.

per, nickel, zinc and iron was 86, 79, 71 and 93% respectively for an initial concentration of 20 mg dm⁻³. The relative order of the equilibrium time as well as the extent of adsorption within the series of metal ions can be explained from the atomic radii and Irving-Williams order of stability. It was further observed that with increase in initial concentration from 20 to 100 mg dm⁻³, adsorption decreases significantly for all the metal ions, e.g. Cu^{II} : 86–66%, Zn^{II} : 71–57%, Ni^{II} : 79–43%, Fe^{II} : 93–76%, as observed earlier⁶.

In order to find out the optimum laterite loading the dose was varied from 0.3 to 1.0 g per 50 cm³ of solution keeping all other experimental conditions constant. The minimum amount of laterite corresponding to the maximum solute sorption at a definite solute concentration was taken as the optimum dose. It was found that the percent uptake of metal ions was increased with increased dose. This is due to much more available sites⁶. Maximum adsorption was observed at 0.8 g for all the metal ions. Subsequent experiments were performed keeping the dose of laterite fixed at 1.0 g. The extent of adsorption increase was found to be Cu^{II} : 39–86%, Zn^{II} : 30–71%, Ni^{II} : 37–79%, Fe^{II} : 51–93%. Smaller particles, due to larger surface area adsorb more metal ions. At a fixed initial metal concentration of 20 mg dm⁻³ the extent of adsorption decreases from for Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Fe^{II} are from 86–32% for Cu^{II}, 71–27% for Zn^{II}, 79–30% for Ni^{II} and 93–44% for Fe^{II} with change of particle size from 300–800 μm.

The agitation speed also has its effects on metal ion adsorption. The percent increase in adsorption, with increase in agitation speed from 100 to 400 rpm was found to be Cu^{II} : 46–86%, Zn^{II} : 41–71%, Ni^{II} : 51–79%, Fe^{II} : 63–93%. With increased agitation speed resistance to mass transfer decreases effecting increased adsorption as we observed earlier⁶.

Adsorption behaviour of different metal ions with increase in temperature from 293–313 K indicates an increase from 66–82% for Cu^{II}, 57–74% for Zn^{II}, 43–58% for Ni^{II} and 76–89% for Fe^{II} with a fixed initial metal concentration (100 mg dm⁻³). Such behaviour may arise from the increased equilibrium constant or activation of adsorption sites at increased temperature or due to a combined effect⁷. The adsorption in the present situation is therefore of endothermic nature.

Adsorption of solute on a solid surface is known to be dependent on the pH of the solution as the surface charge, characterized by pHz_{PC} (zero point charge), of an adsorbent vary with pH. At pH < pHz_{PC} the surface charge is

positive, at pH = pHz_{PC} the surface charge is neutral and at pH > pHz_{PC} the surface charge is negative. The metal oxides present in laterite form aquo complexes with water and develop charged surface through amphoteric dissociation. It is expected that at pH > pHz_{PC} the negative charge density on laterite surface increases, leading to increased adsorption of cationic solute. Simultaneously the pH dependent speciation of solutes play important role. In order to avoid the hydrolysis of metal ions and complexity in speciation all the experiment were performed below pH 6.5.

The role of anions, complexing ligands and co-metal ions on the adsorption of different metal ions were investigated at the equilibrium adsorption condition. Nitrate, phosphate and acetate ions do not interfere. Fluoride, cyanide and EDTA markedly decrease the uptake of all the metal ions studied. Iodide and thiocyanate ions interfere the uptake of copper ion significantly. With the operational pH value neither alkali metal ions [Na^I, K^I] nor alkaline earth metal ions [Ca^{II}, Mg^{II}, Mn^{II} and Al^{III}] adsorb on laterite. The tolerance limit of various ions and salts are furnished in Table 1.

Adsorption isotherm : Adsorption isotherms represent the equilibrium distribution of solute between the aqueous and solid phases with the increase of solute concentration. Equilibrium data are conveniently represented by adsorption isotherm that is helpful in determining the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent. The equilibrium adsorption data in the present case was fitted to Langmuir and Freundlich models and corresponding constants were calculated through linear regression in a condition of best fit.

The linearised Langmuir equation may be represented by⁸

$$C_e/q_e = 1/Qb + C_e/Q$$

where, C_e is equilibrium concentration of metal in solution (mg dm⁻³), q_e is the amount of metal adsorbed at equilibrium (mg g⁻¹) and Q and b are the Langmuir constants, Q signifies the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent and b is related to energy of adsorption process. The Q and b were obtained from the slope and intercept from the linear regression plots of C_e/q_e against C_e (Fig. 2a).

The Freundlich isotherm can be represented by the linear equation as,

$$\ln q_e = \ln K_f + 1/n \ln C_e$$

where, K_f and n are Freundlich constants, with C_e and q_e bearing usual significances. Plot of $\log q_e$ against $\log C_e$

Table 1. Effect and tolerance limit of different salts

Salt	Tolerance limit (μg)				Effect
	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Fe ^{II}	
NaCl, NaNO ₃ , KCl, KNO ₃ , NH ₄ Cl	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	Unchanged
CH ₃ COONa	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	Unchanged
NH ₄ F	100	150	150	150	Decrease
KI	100	250	250	250	Decrease
KCNS	150	200	200	250	Decrease
NaCN	20	30	30	30	Decrease
EDTA	5	5	10	5	Decrease
CaCl ₂ , MgCl ₂ , AlCl ₃ , MnCl ₂	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	10 ⁶	Unchanged

Metal ion : 50 cm³ (100 mg dm⁻³) at the optimum experimental condition.

(Fig. 2a) result K_f and $1/n$ from intercept and slope respectively (Table 2) through linear regression analysis. For both Langmuir and Freundlich models regression coefficient value (R^2) was evaluated for comparison. The results reveal that Freundlich model is best fitted (having higher R^2 value) than Langmuir model.

The free energy change (ΔG) of adsorption was evaluated from the equilibrium constant (K_c) following the relation

$$\Delta G = -RT \ln K_c$$

and ΔH and ΔS was evaluated following van't Hoff equation as⁹,

$$-\Delta G = T\Delta S - \Delta H$$

$$\text{or } R \ln K_c = \Delta S - \Delta H/T$$

Plot of $R \ln K_c$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 2b) gives ΔS from intercept and ΔH from slope. Negative values of ΔG at all temperatures indicate the feasibility of the process and

spontaneous nature of adsorption. The positive values of enthalpy change (ΔH) suggest the endothermic nature while positive ΔS value reflects the affinity of the chosen adsorbent towards metal ions.

The removal efficiency of metal ions¹⁰ was calculated as,

$$RE = (C_0 - C_e)/C_0 \times 100$$

where, C_0 and C_e represent initial and equilibrium metal ion concentration respectively. The higher value of RE (>70%, Table 2) indicate the suitability of the adsorbent as an alternative to activated carbon. The use of active carbon is limited due to its high cost. On the other hand, laterite is readily available in plenty in India as natural occurring geo-material. Considering the removal efficiency, laterite can be used as cost effective adsorbent for metal ions removal process. The adsorption capacity of each metal ion is indicated in Table 2. The effectiveness of the method is tested with the effluent of a typical electroplating industry for the removal of Ni^{II}. A maximum removal of 85% of the total Ni^{II} load is achieved from the waste water composition : pH : 7.9, Ni²⁺ : 82.0 mg dm⁻³, CN⁻ : 0.2 mg dm⁻³, Cd²⁺ : 24.01 mg dm⁻³, Pb²⁺ : 21.2 mg dm⁻³, NH₄⁺-N : 50.0 mg dm⁻³.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of reagent grade. Stock solutions (1000 mg dm⁻³) of Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Fe^{II} were prepared by dissolving the respective metal sulphate in doubly distilled water. Laterite sample obtained from Bankura, (West Bengal, India) was washed with doubly distilled water, air-dried and sieved at different size fractions (viz. 300, 500 and 800 μm) using scientific molecular sieves (Geologists' Syndicate, Kolkata, India).

An atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Varian AA

Fig. 2a. Plot of Langmuir (■) and (◇) Freundlich isotherm.

Fig. 2b. Plot of van't Hoff equation.

Table 2. Removal efficiency and isotherm parameters

Metal ion	Q ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)	$b\cdot 10^2$ ($\text{dm}^3\text{ mg}^{-1}$)	R^2	K_f ($\text{dm}^3\text{ g}^{-1}$)	$1/n$	R^2	RE (%)	Capacity ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$)
Cu ^{II}	4.64	6.56	0.9437	2.05	0.5345	0.9973	86	73.6
Zn ^{II}	5.57	2.35	0.9687	4.78	0.6933	1.0000	71	85.7
Ni ^{II}	2.59	7.11	0.9498	2.23	0.3766	0.9860	79	44.6
Fe ^{II}	4.98	12.89	0.9689	1.28	0.5005	0.9999	93	90.5

Table 3. Characteristic parameters for AAS measurement

Metal ion	Wavelength (nm)	Detection	Sensitivity	Optimum concn.	Standard
		limit	(mg dm^{-3})	range	deviation
Cu ^{II}	324.7	0.011	0.10	0.20–10.0	0.11
Zn ^{II}	232.0	0.020	0.15	0.31–10.0	0.04
Ni ^{II}	213.9	0.005	0.02	0.05–2.0	0.06
Fe ^{II}	248.3	0.021	0.12	0.31–10.0	0.08

1407, USA) was used for determination of metal ions. Systronics pH meter, model no. 324 was used to measure the pH of the aqueous solutions. In AAS an air-acetylene flame was used with the observation at 10 cm above the burner with the characteristic wavelength for specific metals¹². The characteristic parameters for measurement through AAS are indicated in Table 3. The quality assurance and standardisation of each determination was made with standard metal ion solution (Certipure^(R), E. Merck, Germany). X-Ray diffraction data was recorded on a Rigaku Miniflex diffractometer, Japan, model no. ME 200CY2. The Environmental Scanning Electron Microscope, Philips, Model ESEM-(XL-30), Netherlands, was used to record the micrograph.

Batch experiment was conducted to optimise the operational conditions, to determine the capacity of laterite, and the kinetics of adsorption process. 50 cm³ of metal solution after pH adjustment was equilibrated with 1.0 g of laterite in a batch reactor. The amount of metal ion (q_t) adsorbed on laterite, at different time (t) was calculated as,

$$q_t = (C_0 - C_t) \cdot V/W$$

where, C_0 and C_t are the liquid phase metal concentrations (mg dm^{-3}) initially and at t respectively, V is the volume (dm^3) of solution and W is the weight (g) of laterite. The experiments were repeated at least five and the mean values were taken.

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